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Influencia de la inteligencia emocional de los directivos en la formación del estilo de gestión en organizaciones socialmente orientadas

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Resumen. El estudio tuvo como objetivo comprender la relación específica entre la inteligencia emocional de los directivos, la calidad de la comunicación gerencial y la motivación no material de los empleados en organizaciones con orientación social. Además, fue importante identificar los mecanismos a través de los cuales estos factores influyen en la resiliencia organizacional en las condiciones de financiación limitada que enfrentan las organizaciones que operan en el ámbito social. Comprender estos mecanismos es esencial para mejorar la estabilidad del personal y la eficacia de las organizaciones sociales cuando los recursos son limitados. Se utilizó un diseño de investigación mixto. La etapa cuantitativa incluyó una encuesta a 320 empleados de 12 organizaciones sociales utilizando métodos validados: EQ-i 2.0 para evaluar la inteligencia emocional, un cuestionario de calidad de la comunicación gerencial, una escala WEIMS modificada para la motivación no material y una escala ORS adaptada para la resiliencia organizacional. La etapa cualitativa incluyó 24 entrevistas semiestructuradas con directivos y empleados. El análisis se realizó mediante métodos no paramétricos y codificación temática. Los resultados del estudio revelan cuatro mecanismos clave de influencia: apoyo emocional, apertura en la comunicación, reconocimiento de logros y participación en la toma de decisiones. La calidad de la comunicación gerencial es el principal mecanismo a través del cual la inteligencia emocional afecta la motivación de los empleados. Los hallazgos corroboran la necesidad de desarrollar competencias comunicativas en la dirección de organizaciones con orientación social.

Palabras clave: comunicaciones gerenciales, motivación no material, sostenibilidad organizacional, retención de personal, trabajo social.

Influence of managers' emotional intelligence on the formation of management style in socially oriented organizations

Abstract. The study was aimed at understanding the specific relationship between managers' emotional intelligence, the quality of managerial communications, and employees' non-material motivation in socially oriented organizations. In addition, it was important to identify the mechanisms through which these factors influence organizational resilience under the conditions of limited funding faced by organizations operating in the social sphere. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for improving staff stability and the effectiveness of social organizations when resources are constrained. A mixed research design was used. The quantitative stage included a survey of 320 employees from 12 social organizations using validated methods: EQ-i 2.0 to assess emotional intelligence, a managerial communication quality questionnaire, a modified WEIMS scale for non-material motivation, and an adapted ORS scale for organizational resilience. The qualitative stage included 24 semi-structured interviews with managers and employees. Analysis was conducted using non-parametric methods and thematic coding. The results of the study reveal four key mechanisms of influence: emotional support, openness in communication, recognition of achievements, and participation in decision-making. The quality of managerial communications is the main mechanism through which emotional intelligence affects employee motivation. The findings substantiate the need to develop communication competences among the management of socially oriented organizations.

Key words: management communications, non-material motivation, organizational sustainability, staff retention, social work.

INTRODUCTION

In the field of human resource management, the sphere of social work as an attractive area of employment constantly faces high staff turnover, emotional burnout among specialists, and a decline in the quality of social services (Donika et al., 2024; Sapfirova, 2025). Under the conditions of limited funding (Krokhina, 2024), which is typical of socially oriented organizations, traditional mechanisms of financial incentives are often unavailable, making non-material motivation a key factor in staff retention (Janani & Pougajendy, 2024; Nikolaeva et al., 2023).

Recent studies show that the quality of interaction between management and employees has a much stronger impact on motivation than financial incentives in the context of social work (Midlage, 2025).

The research problem lies in identifying mechanisms to increase the effectiveness of managerial communications in influencing non-material motivation in the context of socially oriented organizations, where employees work under the conditions of high emotional stress and limited financial resources (Togaibayeva et al., 2023). In this context, the emotional intelligence of managers becomes a critical factor as it allows them to effectively manage their own emotional state and that of subordinates, create a psychologically safe work environment, and develop sustainable motivational mechanisms that do not require significant financial costs (Hwang, 2024; Midlage, 2025).

The objective of the study is to identify and describe the interconnections between managers' emotional intelligence, the quality of managerial communications, and the formation of employees' non-material motivation in socially oriented organizations, as well as to determine the mechanisms through which these factors influence organizational resilience under conditions of limited funding.

LITERATURE REVIEW

First, scholars draw attention to the influence of managers' emotional intelligence on creating a comfortable environment for employees (Yang, 2025), which is a key predictor of job satisfaction and employee engagement under the conditions of limited funding (Belozorova, 2025; Muñoz et al., 2024). Employees with a high level of emotional intelligence demonstrate greater resilience to stress factors and stronger commitment to organizational values.

Azad and Kumar (2023) identified a direct relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being in the workplace. Their study showed that emotionally intelligent managers create an atmosphere of psychological safety, which becomes a powerful non-material motivator for employees of social organizations. Nugraha (2024) found that emotional intelligence plays a key role in reducing staff turnover. The author demonstrated that emotional communication helps lower stress levels and retain personnel by fostering positive relationships and strengthening organizational commitment.

Second, the quality of managerial communications is regarded as an essential factor of organizational effectiveness in the social sector (Abdullaev, 2023). Hwang (2024) claimed that managers' emotional intelligence significantly improves communication, strengthens trust, and increases employee engagement, which is especially important in the context of socially oriented organizations. Messaoudi and Sakale (2024) found that managers' interpersonal skills, based on emotional intelligence, serve as a gateway to creating an emotionally intelligent work environment. The authors emphasize that adaptive communication styles and active listening contribute to conflict resolution, the strengthening of trust, and greater influence on the team.

Third, socially oriented organizations are characterized by a link between managers' emotional intelligence and employees' work style, which affects their motivational mechanisms (Kryucheva & Tolstoukhova, 2024). Wijaya and Senen (2024) argue that in social organizations, special attention is given to value-based communication and inclusive decision-making under the conditions of limited resources. Timbaliuc (2022) found a correlation between high levels of managers' emotional intelligence and a democratic style of communication. This study has shown that emotionally intelligent leaders are more inclined to involve subordinates in decision-making processes, which enhances their motivation and organizational commitment.

Despite the considerable amount of research devoted to emotional intelligence and its impact on organizational outcomes, there are several gaps that require further study.

On the one hand, the specifics of how emotional intelligence manifests in different cultural contexts remain insufficiently explored (Moyinoluwa, 2024; Vengerovsky & Vasiliev, 2024; Almadani, 2025). On the other hand, there is a gap in understanding the mechanisms through which managerial communications influence the formation of non-material motivation in socially oriented organizations (Babina & Utusikov, 2024). Butko (2025) notes that modern con-

cepts of emotional intelligence require improvement and greater elaboration regarding decision-making processes.

The study aims at addressing these gaps through a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between managers' emotional intelligence, the quality of managerial communications, and the formation of sustainable non-material motivation in Russian social organizations.

METHODS

Research design

To achieve the research objective, a mixed design was selected, combining quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection and analysis (Almuffih et al., 2024). This approach helps obtain both statistically significant results on the relationships between the main research variables (managers' emotional intelligence, the quality of managerial communications, the level of employees' non-material motivation, and indicators of organizational resilience), as well as a deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which managerial communications influence employee motivation. The quantitative component of the study is correlational and aims to identify statistically significant relationships between managers' emotional intelligence, the quality of managerial communications, the level of employees' non-material motivation, and indicators of organizational resilience.

The qualitative component includes semi-structured interviews with managers and employees of social organizations to provide an in-depth analysis of the mechanisms of motivation formation and identify specific factors influencing staff retention in this field.

Research sample

Quantitative stage. The sample consisted of 320 employees from 12 social organizations located in three regions of the Russian Federation. The focus on private social organizations was determined by the comparability of management styles and organizational structures, which ensures greater homogeneity of the sample and increases the internal validity of the results.

The characteristics of the sample are presented in Table 1.

Typology of participating organizations:

Type 1: Medical centers, private hospitals, hospices, nursing homes, rehabilitation centers, and residential facilities for the elderly.

Type 2: Charitable foundations (private, family, corporate, or community-based), autonomous non-profit organizations, and public associations.

Type 3: Psychological support centers, educational and career guidance centers, and professional rehabilitation organizations.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria for the participants are presented in Figure 1.

TABLE 1. Sample characteristics and distribution of participants by type of organization.

Characteristics	Value
General characteristics of the sample	
Total sample size	n=320
Managers	n=85 (26.6%)
Employees	n=235 (73.4%)
Number of organizations	12
Regions covered by the study	Moscow, Saint Petersburg, Nizhny Novgorod
Demographic characteristics	
Average age of participants	38.4 years (SD=11.2)
Gender distribution	74% women, 26% men
Average length of service in the organization	4.8 years (SD=3.6)
Distribution of participants by type of organization	
Private social organizations providing socio-medical services	n=128 (40.0%)
Private social organizations engaged in charitable activities	n=96 (30.0%)
Private social organizations offering psychological, educational, and labor assistance	n=96 (30.0%)

FIGURE 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for study participants.

Qualitative phase. For the in-depth interviews, a purposive sample of 24 participants was formed (12 managers and 12 employees) representing different types of social organizations: Type 1 organizations (n=8), Type 2 organizations (n=8), and Type 3 organizations (n=8).

Research instruments

For the quantitative phase, the following psychodiagnostic tools were used (Table 2).

TABLE 2. Psychodiagnostic tools used in the quantitative phase of the study.

Tool	Construct measured	Number of questions	Components/scales	Reliability (α)
Emotional intelligence questionnaire EQ-i 2.0 (Bar-On, 2006)	Emotional intelligence of managers	133	Self-perception, self-expression, interpersonal skills, decision-making, stress management	0.89
Managerial communication quality questionnaire (Spitzberg & Cupach, 2011)	Effectiveness of managerial communication	28	Effectiveness, clarity, empathy, adaptability of communication	0.92
Non-material motivation scale in social work (modified version of WEIMS) (Tremblay et al., 2009)	Non-material motivation of employees	18	Intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation	0.87
Organizational resilience questionnaire (adapted ORS) (Kantur & İşeri-Say, 2012)	Organizational resilience	24	Adaptability, cohesion, stress resistance, recovery effectiveness	0.85

Data collection procedure

Data were collected between March and June 2024. Quantitative data were gathered using the online platform SurveyMonkey, ensuring complete anonymity of participants. Each respondent was assigned a unique code to match data from managers and subordinates without compromising their confidentiality.

Qualitative interviews were conducted in person, either on the premises of participating organizations or in a neutral setting chosen by the interviewees. The duration of each interview was 45-60 minutes. All interviews were recorded with participants' consent and subsequently transcribed for analysis.

The full confidentiality of participants' personal data was ensured.

Data analysis methods

The analysis of quantitative data included calculating descriptive statistics to characterize the sample and testing for normality of distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Since the survey data did not follow a normal distribution ($p < 0.05$), non-parametric methods were used for analyzing relationships. Correlation analysis was conducted using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient to identify relationships between the studied variables. Groups were compared using the Mann-Whitney test (for two independent groups) and the Kruskal-Wallis test (for multiple comparisons). Multiple regression analysis was performed using ordinal regression to identify predictors of non-material motivation with due regard to the ordinal nature of the survey data. To test the mediating role of managerial communications, mediation analysis was conducted using bootstrap procedures for non-parametric data.

Qualitative analysis was carried out using thematic coding according to the approach in (Braun & Clarke, 2006), including initial coding of interview transcripts, grouping codes into thematic categories, identifying key themes and patterns, and triangulating the results with quanti-

tative data. Statistical processing was performed with the SPSS 28.0 software. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ensuring reliability and validity

Internal validity was ensured through the use of validated psychodiagnostic methods, control of confounding variables (work experience, age, level of education), and the application of strict inclusion/exclusion criteria.

External validity was enhanced by including organizations of different types and sizes from various regions, which allows for generalizing the results to a broader population of social organizations.

The reliability of qualitative data was ensured through a double-coding procedure (two independent coders), followed by the calculation of intercoder reliability (Cohen's Kappa=0.84).

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics

A test of normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov criterion showed that the data on all scales significantly deviated from a normal distribution ($p < 0.05$), which justified the use of non-parametric methods of analysis.

TABLE 3. Descriptive statistics of the main research variables.

Variable	n	Median	Q1-Q3	Min-Max	Average	SD
Managers' emotional intelligence (EQ-i 2.0)	85	112.0	96.0-126.0	65.0-142.0	109.7	18.4
Quality of management communications	320	87.0	76.0-99.0	43.0-124.0	86.3	16.2
Non-material employee motivation (WEIMS)	235	65.0	56.0-74.0	30.0-88.0	63.8	13.7
Organizational resilience (ORS)	320	76.0	67.0-86.0	39.0-106.0	75.9	15.1

Median values across all scales fall within the average to above-average range (Table 3), indicating a relatively favorable situation in the organizations studied.

The analysis of relationships between variables was conducted using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (Table 4).

TABLE 4. Correlation matrix of the main research variables.

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. Managers' emotional intelligence	-			
2. Quality of managerial communications	0.672***	-		
3. Employees' non-material motivation	0.524***	0.681***	-	
4. Organizational resilience	0.618***	0.743***	0.706***	-

*** $p < 0.001$.

Statistically significant positive correlations were found between all the studied variables. The strongest relationship was identified between the quality of managerial communications and organizational resilience.

Comparisons between managers and rank-and-file employees were conducted using the Mann-Whitney test (Table 5).

TABLE 5. Differences in ratings between managers and employees.

Variable	Managers (n=85) Median (Q1-Q3)	Employees (n=235) Median (Q1-Q3)	U	Z	p	r
Quality of management communications	94.0 (84.0-107.0)	83.0 (73.0-95.0)	6342.5	-4.87	< 0.001	0.27
Organizational resilience	83.0 (74.0-93.0)	73.0 (64.0-83.0)	6891.0	-4.23	< 0.001	0.24

Managers reported significantly higher ratings of communication quality and organizational resilience compared to rank-and-file employees.

Differences among the three types of social organizations were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test (Table 6).

TABLE 6. Differences in indicators among types of organizations.

Variable	Type 1 (n=96)	Type 2 (n=96)	Type 3 (n=128)	H	p	η^2
Managers' emotional intelligence	116.0 (103.0-129.0)	113.0 (99.0-125.0)	105.0 (92.0-119.0)	8.94	0.011	0.11
Quality of management communications	91.0 (80.0-103.0)	89.0 (78.0-101.0)	82.0 (72.0-93.0)	12.67	0.002	0.08
Non-material motivation	69.0 (60.0-77.0)	67.0 (58.0-75.0)	61.0 (53.0-70.0)	15.89	< 0.001	0.14
Organizational resilience	80.0 (71.0-89.0)	78.0 (69.0-87.0)	72.0 (63.0-81.0)	11.23	0.004	0.07

*Data are presented as median (25th-75th percentile).

The analysis revealed statistically significant differences among the three types of organizations across all the measured indicators. Type 1 organizations showed the highest median values: managers' emotional intelligence (116.0), quality of managerial communications (91.0), employees' non-material motivation (69.0), and organizational resilience (80.0). The lowest values were observed in Type 3 organizations.

To examine the mediating role of managerial communications in the relationship between managers’ emotional intelligence and employees’ non-material motivation, a mediation analysis was conducted using a bootstrap procedure (5,000 iterations) (Table 7).

TABLE 7. Mediation analysis results.

Trajectory	Coefficient	SE	95% CI	p
a (Emotional intelligence → Communication)	0.672	0.084	0.507-0.837	< 0.001
b (Communication → Motivation)	0.681	0.061	0.561-0.801	< 0.001
c (total effect: Emotional intelligence → Motivation)	0.524	0.074	0.379-0.669	< 0.001
c' (direct effect with mediator controlled)	0.067	0.082	-0.094-0.228	0.413
ab (indirect effect via mediator)	0.457	0.071	0.318-0.596	< 0.001

The results show full mediation: when the quality of managerial communications is included as a mediator, the direct relationship between managers’ emotional intelligence and employees’ non-material motivation becomes non-significant (p=0.413). The mediation effect accounts for 87.2%.

Qualitative analysis results

The thematic analysis of 24 interviews identified four main themes that explain the mechanisms through which managers’ emotional intelligence influences employee motivation.

Theme 1: “Emotional support and understanding” (mentioned by all 24 participants)

The participants emphasized the importance of emotional support from management: *“In our work, it is very important to feel that the manager understands your state and can support you in a difficult moment”* (Employee, Type 1 organization, 5 years of experience).

Theme 2: “Openness and accessibility in communication” (21 participants)

Employees highly valued the possibility of open dialogue with management: *“When you can approach the manager with any question and know that you will be heard, it gives confidence and the desire to work better”* (Manager, Type 2 organization, 7 years of experience).

Theme 3: “Recognition of professional achievements” (19 participants)

Non-material recognition was seen as an important motivating factor: *“Our salaries are modest, but when the manager acknowledges your work in front of colleagues or thanks you in writing, it is very meaningful”* (Employee, Type 1 organization, 4 years of experience).

Theme 4: “Participation in decision-making” (16 participants)

The opportunity to influence work processes increased engagement: *“When we are asked for our opinions on work matters and our suggestions are considered, you feel like part of the team”* (Employee, Type 3 organization, 6 years of experience).

The comparison of quantitative and qualitative data revealed a high degree of consistency. The statistically identified mediating role of managerial communications is supported by qualitative evidence highlighting the importance of open dialogue and emotional support. Differences between organization types are explained by the specific organizational culture and the nature of activities identified during the interviews.

DISCUSSION

The most significant finding is the identification of full mediation in the relationship between managers' emotional intelligence and employees' non-material motivation through the quality of managerial communications, with 87.2% of the effect being mediated by communication processes.

This result broadens the understanding of the mechanisms of emotional intelligence in the organizational context, showing that its influence on motivation is realized mainly through the quality of communication processes rather than directly (Moturenko, 2023; Dzgoev et al., 2024). This is consistent with studies (Hwang, 2024; Messaoudi & Sakale, 2024) that emphasized the role of emotional intelligence in improving interpersonal interaction and creating an emotionally intelligent work environment.

The strong correlations identified between the studied variables ($r_s=0.524-0.743$) point to the systemic interaction between emotional intelligence, communications, motivation, and organizational resilience. Particularly noteworthy is the relationship between the quality of managerial communications and organizational resilience ($r_s=0.743$), which confirms the key role of communication processes in ensuring the stability of social organizations under the conditions of limited funding.

The results of the study are consistent with the findings of (Muñoz et al., 2024), which indicate that emotional intelligence is a key predictor of job satisfaction and employee engagement in the conditions of limited funding. However, this study expands on these findings by showing the specific mechanisms of influence through managerial communications.

The identified importance of emotional support and recognition of professional achievements as key themes of the qualitative analysis confirms (Silva, 2024; Kochetkova et al., 2025) the role of emotional intelligence in shaping a positive workplace culture (Mikhailenko, 2024). At the same time, the results complement the study (Timbaliuc, 2022), demonstrating not only the correlation between emotional intelligence and democratic communication, but also explaining the mechanism of this relationship through the improvement of communication quality.

The differences in assessments between managers and employees revealed in this study are consistent with the observations (Carter, 2024) regarding positional differences in the perception of organizational processes. However, the obtained data show that these differences do not hinder the formation of general patterns in the relationships between the studied variables.

The qualitative analysis confirms the conclusions (Janani & Pougajendy, 2024) on the critical importance of emotional intelligence for reducing emotional burnout and increasing team resilience. The identified theme of emotional support and understanding directly corresponds to their findings about the role of emotional intelligence in creating an atmosphere of psychological safety.

The results obtained contribute to the development of motivation theory in socially oriented organizations by demonstrating specific mechanisms for forming non-material motivation. The mediating role of managerial communications broadens the understanding of how managers' emotional intelligence influences organizational outcomes.

The results confirm the applicability of social exchange theory in the context of social organizations, showing how high-quality communicative relationships between management and employees compensate for the limited possibilities of material incentives. Emotional support, recognition of achievements, and participation in decision-making serve as non-material currencies of social exchange.

The study also develops the understanding of organizational sustainability in the social sphere, demonstrating that it is shaped not only through financial stability but also through the quality of human relationships and the emotional climate within the organization. This expands traditional models of sustainability by adding emotional and communicative components.

For the managers of social organizations, the results of the study stipulate the need to prioritize the development of communication competences alongside emotional intelligence (Fedotova et al., 2025). Since the quality of managerial communications is the main mechanism through which emotional intelligence affects employee motivation, investments in developing the communication skills of management may have the greatest impact under the conditions of limited resources.

The identified differences between organization types suggest the necessity of a differentiated approach to personnel management. Type 1 organizations, which demonstrated the highest results across all parameters, may serve as a model for other types of social organizations in terms of organizing communication processes and developing employees' emotional intelligence.

The qualitative results provide recommendations for practical application: ensuring management is accessible for dialogue, creating a system for recognizing professional achievements, and involving employees in decision-making processes. These measures do not require significant financial resources but can substantially increase motivation and reduce staff turnover.

For social organizations, the study results substantiate incorporating emotional intelligence criteria into management recruitment procedures, as well as the need for systematic training in communication skills at all levels of management (Kovalenko et al., 2022; Abdullayev et al., 2024).

Study limitations

The cross-sectional nature of the quantitative stage does not allow for definitive conclusions about cause-and-effect relationships. Although the mediation analysis provides compelling evidence of the direction of effects, longitudinal studies could offer more robust confirmation of the identified patterns.

The regional limitation of the sample (three regions of the Russian Federation) may reduce the generalizability of the results to other cultural and socio-economic contexts. The specifics of the Russian social work system and the characteristics of national culture may influence the nature of the observed relationships (Alekseeva & Zubova, 2024; Pashkurov et al., 2025).

The use of self-reports by participants to assess all variables may lead to social desirability effects and common method variance. Including objective measures of organizational performance and independent assessments of communication processes could enhance the validity of the results.

The qualitative component of the study is limited by a relatively small sample of interviews (24 participants), which may not fully capture the diversity of opinions and experiences of employees in social organizations. A larger qualitative study could reveal additional themes and nuances.

Directions for future research

Longitudinal studies could track the dynamics of managers' emotional intelligence development and its impact on employee motivation over time, which would allow for a more accurate establishment of cause-and-effect relationships and an assessment of the stability of the identified effects.

Cross-cultural studies are required to test the universality of the identified patterns in different cultural contexts. A key area of interest lies in comparing the processes that drive non-material motivation in countries with diverse social welfare frameworks and social work structures.

Intervention studies aimed at developing managers' emotional intelligence and communication skills could test the effectiveness of the identified patterns and help design evidence-based training programs for the social sector (Akhmetshin et al., 2025).

The study of the role of emotional intelligence under remote and hybrid work conditions, which are becoming increasingly widespread in the social sector, represents a relevant direction for future research, especially in the context of post-crisis organizational development.

CONCLUSIONS

This study made a significant contribution to understanding the mechanisms of non-material motivation in socially oriented organizations, revealing the key role of managers' emotional intelligence and the quality of managerial communications. The main result was the identification of full mediation in the relationship between managers' emotional intelligence and employees' non-material motivation through the quality of managerial communications, with 87.2% of the effect being mediated by communication processes.

The study demonstrated that, under the conditions of limited funding in social organizations, emotional support, open communication, recognition of professional achievements, and participation in decision-making become the main factors of employee motivation. The differences identified between types of organizations indicate the need for a differentiated approach to human resource management in the social sector.

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